

THE ROLE OF "KOYATOSH" PAINTINGS IN STUDYING THE SPIRITUAL AND RELIGIOUS LIFE OF ANCIENT PEOPLE

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Abstract: *In this article, the authors provided information about the role of "Kayatosh" paintings in the study of the way of life, economy, and spiritual and religious life of ancient people. Here, the history of the study of "Kayatosh" paintings is briefly covered, and it is explained that the cycle of images dedicated to various topics spans several thousand years.*

Key words: *"Kayatosh" paintings, Altamira cave, Kapova cave, Bukantog, Zarautsoy, Saymolitash, Sarmishsoy, images of animals, Takatosh, Karakiyasoy, Okchobsoy, M. Khojanazarov, A. Kholmatov, human images.*

In the current science of world history, attention is paid to "Kayatosh" paintings as a historical source, and extensive use of modern methods of research is being carried out in their conservation and repair, periodic dating, classification, and determining their place in the development of world civilization. In this regard, UNESCO, the international organization for preservation of cultural heritage monuments, has recognized that rock paintings are a historical and cultural heritage monument that is widely distributed around the world and that they are a primary source of valuable information about the life of our ancient ancestors.¹

In the years of independence, great attention has been paid to the studies of the worldview and ethnoculture of mankind, which have developed from the Paleolithic period to the present day. During the past time, the collection of new archaeological materials, the improvement of the methods and methods of their

¹ Холматов А.Н. Нурота тоғ тизмасы қоятош расмнари техника-типологияси ва тарихий таҳлили. Тарих фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дисс... Самарқанд, 2019. Б. 3.

processing require obtaining new scientific conclusions in this regard.²

The unfortunate aspect of the problem is that the total number of monuments associated with rock paintings has not yet been fully accounted for. Targeted archaeological expeditions and special studies have been conducted for many years to determine their number. But these researches were carried out unevenly. "Kayatosh" paintings are dedicated to various topics, covering the life and religious concepts of ancient people. These paintings are examples of the elegant art of our ancient ancestors and are considered an integral part of fine art. One of the reasons these paintings have historical significance is that they span several millennia. The most ancient rock paintings in our country belong to the fourth and third millennia BC, that is, to the Neolithic and Eneolithic periods. Their age can also be determined by comparing them with archeological finds and paintings from other similar places.

" Kayatosh " has been interesting to scientists for almost 250 years, and it has its own trick of study. The first rock paintings in human history were discovered in the Altamira cave in Spain on the Iberian Peninsula. Altamira (La cueva de Altamira) is a cave in Spain that contains polychrome rock paintings from the Upper Paleolithic (Solutrean culture). The study of the rock paintings here began in 1868 when it was discovered by hunter Modest Cubillas Peras³. At that time, the discovery of the cave was a big news for archeology.

This cave was first explored in 1880 by Sautuola and Juan Vilanova y Piera, an archaeologist from the University of Madrid, who identified the drawings as belonging to the Paleolithic period. Excavations in the cave were carried out in 1902-1904, 1924-1925, 1960-1970, and 1981. Since its discovery, this cave has been studied by all the leading Paleolithic paleontologists. The cave paintings are mainly from the Madeleine and Solturean cultures, who used the cave at various times for about 22,000 years, until the entrance was blocked by a landslide, about 35,600-13,000 years ago.

One of such rock images in the history of mankind was studied in the Kapova

² Хўжаназаров М. Сармишсой (қоятош расмлари) ва таърихий тадқиқотлар). - Тошкент, 2018. - Б. 22.

³ Дэвлет Е. Г. [Альтамира: у истоков искусства](#). М.: Алетея, 2004. С. 277.

cave of the Republic of Bashkortostan, Russian Federation. This cave is famous for the Late Solutrean to Middle Madeleine rock carvings of Paleolithic primitive man. P. I. Rychkov (1760) and I. Lepekhin (1770) are the first explorers of the caves. The name of this cave was called Shulgantash by local residents, and the ancient inhabitants - Bashkirs - used this place as a shelter during the wars. The petroglyphs here are mostly preserved on the smooth wall at the far end of the Hall of Chaos on the first floor. The drawings were discovered in 1959 by the reserve zoologist A. V. Ryumin. The Institute of Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR (O.N. Bader and V.E. Shchelinsky) played a major role in the study of ancient painting. Later, it is studied by the All-Russian Institute of Geology (Y.S. Lyakhnitsky), Geographical Society. Thanks to his research, 173 drawings or their remains - color spots - have been identified⁴

The drawings are mostly painted with ocher paint mixed with animal fat, they are about 18 thousand years old, mammoths, horses and other animals, anthropomorphic figures are depicted.

Our country is also famous for its rock paintings. On the scale of the territory of Uzbekistan, rock paintings of historical periods from the Mesolithic period to the present day have been studied. Monuments of this type were first created on the eve of the invasion of the Russian Empire and in 1834 by the Russian army officer P.I. It was identified by Demezov in the rocks of Bukantog in Kyzylkum regions⁵. Later, N.A., a member of the Turkestan Amateur Archeology Club. Nasledov, N.I. Veselovsky, V.V. Barthold, A.S. Tatarinov, M.S. Andreev, G.I. Pantusov, V.I. Scientists such as Masalsky have carried out some research on rock paintings. Sarmishsay rock paintings have a special place among them.⁶

Among the rock paintings found in Central Asia, the Zarautsoi monument is the most ancient and unique. Zarautkamar Cave is located in the Zarautsoy Gorge,

⁴ [Ляхницкий Ю. С.](#) Сокровище палеолита: рисунки и знаки пещеры Шульганташ. Уфа: Китап, 2008. С. 187

⁵ Демезон П.И. Записки о Бухарском ханстве (отчеты П.И. Демезона и И.В. Веткевича). - М., 1983. - С. 17-83.

⁶ Кабиров Ж. Сармишсойнинг қоятошларидаги расмлар. - Тошкент, 1976; Хужаназаров М.М. Наскальные изображения Ходжакента и Каракияся. - Самарканд, 1995.

at the northeastern foothills of Kohitangtog, the southwestern branch of the Khisar mountain range. The monument is administratively located 5 km south of Kizilolma village, Sherabad district, Surkhandarya region, 2000 m above sea level. Research work in Zarautsoya was initially carried out by G.V. Parfyonov, 48 different pictures were identified and described. Over the years, the Zarautsoi stone monument has been owned by I. F. Lomaev, G. V. Parfyonov, A. Yu. Roginskaya, A. S. Kirillov, A. A. Formozov, A. P. Ivanova, V. K. Sandul, Sh. It was studied by Ismailov, A. Kabirov and M. Khojanazarov.⁷ Zarautsoi paintings are a product of the artistic creation of people of the Stone Age, a rare example of rock art. As a result of the conducted scientific expeditions, 264 pictures located in 26 belts were studied.

In 1969, academician Ya. At the initiative of Ghulomov, a special group studying rock paintings of the Republic was formed under the Institute of History and Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In the years 1969-1975, the employees of this group under the leadership of J. Kabirov carried out extensive research in the side gorges of the Nurota mountain range. monuments of paintings have been discovered and some of them have been partially studied.⁸

The research of rock paintings on the Nurota mountain range in the following years was connected with the researches of M. Khujanazarov on the southern slope of Oktog. In particular, in 1980, new rock paintings were discovered in Burgansoy gorge. The content of the pictures is different, and there are more than 100 pictures of wild animals. They consist of a man, a mountain goat, an arghar, a horse, a camel, a domestic ox, a dog, inscriptions in Arabic and Cyrillic letters and other obscure images. These paintings by ancient artists are 10 cm. from to 30 cm. made in sizes up to M. Khojanazarov studied the working technique, drawing style, degree of burning and preservation of these petroglyphs and dated them to the beginning of the 1st millennium AD.⁹ These new rock art monuments contain thousands of

⁷ Эшқурбонов С.Б. Қоятош тасвирий санъат обидалари таҳлиliga доир баъзи мулоҳазалар//Шарқшунослар анжумани (ТДШН) №9 сони. – Тошкент, 2014. – Б. 99–103.

⁸ Кабиrow Ж. Ибтидоий давр беҳзодлари // Фан ва турмуш. 1-сон. –1970. - Б. 9-11.

⁹ Хужаназаров М. Новые наскальные рисунки Бургансая // ИМКУ. Вып. 19 - Ташкент, 1984. - С. 28-32.

paintings, and more than 50 types have been identified.¹⁰

According to M. Khojanazarov, an archeologist, ancient people used to pray near the painted rocks in this holy shrine and perform religious ceremonies and rituals at certain times. Such information can be observed during the analysis of the meaning of the paintings on the rocks. The religious meaning of some paintings has not lost its status until our days, and they hide the secrets related to the religious practices and rituals of the people of the Eneolithic, Bronze and Scythian periods. According to the old people living near the monuments, in Karaganda, until recently, childless or sick women and men agreed and performed some customs. They worshiped here and made sacrifices. This score was repeated even when the animals were sick. The scraps of cloth tied to the branches of the trees here prove the remnants of such rituals¹¹

For thousands of years, stone paintings, which are an ancient art form, have been depicted by our ancestors for the purpose of paganism, sorcery and other religious concepts and life events related to the life and occupation of people of that time. These paintings are considered not only as great works of art from the ancient peoples, but also as a valuable historical source for the history of the peoples of the world, including the history of Uzbekistan, a wonderful chronicle, large archival materials. The images of the monuments of rock paintings in our country are divided into the following separate groups according to their content.

The most common of them is the image of people, and the images of people were created by ancient artists in a variety of ways. Their legs, arms, and whole body are made in a simple schematic style, while some of them are depicted like the letter F. It should be noted that the images of people in some monuments are created in a realistic way, so they are surprising. The head, body, arms and legs of these human figures are in perfect proportion to each other. In most cases, they were depicted standing or shooting wild animals from a bow. Some people are depicted with arrows, daggers, and swords on their backs. In most of them, the symbol of

¹⁰ Холматов А.Н. Нурота тизмаси қоятош расмларнинг техник-типологик жиҳатдан ўрганилишига доир. Археология Узбекистана. 2016. № 1 (12. Б. 75.

¹¹ Абрамзон С.М. Киргизы и их этнографические и историко-культурные связи. Л.: Наука, 1971. С. 303.

masculinity is exaggerated. There are also pictures of women in the monuments.

Some people depicted are wearing long clothes. In addition, people driving camel caravans, riding on horses or camels, and shepherds (shepherds) are very skillfully carved into the rocks. Such truthfulness in the paintings is evidence of the high skill and taste of the ancient artists¹².

Most of the rock paintings are animal images. These consist of images of wild and domestic animals. Wild animals include primitive bull, primitive cow, mountain goat, arhar, gazelle, saiga, real deer, wild horse, coon, boar, as well as carnivores such as lion, tiger, cheetah, bears or ilvirs, wolf, fox, chiabori and others can be included. Images of snakes and birds are sometimes found on the rocks. Pictures of primitive bulls and cows belong to the oldest rock paintings of the Nurota mountain range. They have large heads, long horns, short necks, broad shoulders, long waists, restrained bodies, and the tip of their tails is pointed. Primitive cow paintings are depicted in the same way as primitive bulls, but differ from them in some aspects. For example; the horns of the primitive cow were not very long and were made in a slightly thinner state¹³.

Image of combat and hunting weapons. This group of pictures can include arrows, swords, daggers, traps and other images. The results of a comprehensive comparative study of arrow-bow images on rocks show that they are of two types in terms of shape, one is simple and the other is complex. A simple bow is made by bending a solid branch and drawing a string, while a complex bow is made of bone, horn and solid wood. In the pictures, a complex arch differs from a simple arch in that its upper part is somewhat concave, and both ends are turned inward. Another type of combat and hunting weapon is the dagger, which is shaft in shape. avv. As early as the 8th-1st centuries, it was depicted as similar to the dagger - akinak, which was common among the Saks, Massagets and neighboring tribes. There are also swords depicted on the waist (or separately) of human figures on the rocks of some

¹² Холматов А.Н. Нурота тизмаси қоятош расмларининг техник-типологик жиҳатдан ўрганилишига доир. Археология Узбекистана. 2016. № 1 (12. Б. 79).

¹³ Холматов А.Н. Нурота тизмаси қоятош расмларининг техник-типологик жиҳатдан ўрганилишига доир... Б. 79.

monuments. The last part of the hilt of the sword is rounded, and a transverse line is visible between the hilt and the blade. It means that it is a device that prevents the hand from going into the edge of the sword. The sword is depicted as having a long blade, which is either straight or slightly curved.

In the image of farm and household items on rocks, it is possible to include the image of a saddle, bridle, stirrup, arrow (sadoq), ax, ax (obdasta), musical instrument (rubob) and other items. However, the depiction of these objects is rare among rock paintings. The image we call a trap is a circle with a long line touching it. This allows us to say that it is depicted as being connected by a rope or chain from one end. Traps of this form are still widely used by people in mountainous areas. Arrows are mainly depicted hanging next to hunters. The ropes are shown tied to domestic animals such as cattle, horses, and camels. In the new rock paintings discovered on the southern slope of the Northern Nurota ridge, saddles, bridles, stirrups, together with the horse or separately, are often found among the images of the later period. Also, among the images belonging to the later period in the Karaqiyasoy rocks located in the Karaqchitog ridge, we find the image of the musical instrument rubob. Pictures of such musical instruments are not found in other monuments of rock paintings in our republic¹⁴.

Images of clothing are rare in northern rock art monuments. They are sometimes depicted in long form on people. It can be chakmon or chapon typical of herding peoples. We can find images of clothes more often among the Sarmishsay rock paintings. On its rocks we see people depicted with clothes. These are helmets, spiked headphones, short coats, high heels, and more.

Images of patterns, rhombuses, stamps, and various obscure (abstract) signs. The images that we assume to be stamps are found on the rocks of the northern Nurota mountain range, and stamps are not found on other rocks in the territory of our country. Stamps have different shapes and appearances. The stamp is one of the most common signs of private property among Turko-Mongolian herding tribes.

¹⁴ Холматов А., Холматов З. Тулкиликамар янги қоятош расмлари хусусида айрим мулоҳазалар. // Ўзбекистон археологияси № 3 (22). Тошкент, 2020. Б. 3-10

They were printed or engraved on weapons, animal skins, coins and other objects. It is noted that images of stamps similar to them exist in similar monuments in the regions of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, and southern Siberia¹⁵. The rhombus is one of the geometric symbols, and its pictures are present in all the monuments of the Nurota mountain range, but there are many rock paintings in the monuments such as Karaqiyasoy and Yonboshsoy. They were very beautifully done by the ancient artist in contour, shadow, shadow-contour and elegant-patterned styles. We can see that red paint-ochre is also drawn over the lines of the rhombus image made on the basis of some hammering techniques in the Karaqiyasoy rock art monument. Such a situation is not found in other rock art monuments in our Republic.

The Turan land was considered one of the most convenient areas for nomadic pastoralist tribes and peoples to raise their livestock and hunt wild animals, for seasonal or permanent residence. These rock paintings are an important historical source for studying the socio-political, economic, spiritual-cultural, religious, and economic life of ancient hunter-gatherer and nomadic steppe tribes and peoples¹⁶. A. Kabirov, one of the specialists who conducted scientific research on the Sarmishsay rock paintings, said, "Most of the rock paintings were concentrated in the remote places far from the eyes of people, and such places were considered one of the most sacred shrines of the primitive and ancient tribes. "The people of that time may have prayed in front of the painted rocks in this sacred shrine and performed various religious ceremonies and rituals." G.V., who studied Zarautsoy's paintings. Parfyonov puts forward the opinion that "Zarautsoi paintings were not drawn to decorate the space and shelters, but primitive people may have painted these paintings in order to easily kill wild animals and to make the hunt successful."

Several experts in the field, while talking about these rock paintings, believe that the images on the rocks may have been made in order to increase the number of livestock and wild animals. In particular, in one of the ethnographic data collected by the authors of the village of Okchobsoy, Koshrabot district, when the elders were

¹⁵ Тошбоев Ф.Э. Взаимовлияние степной и оседлоземледельческой культур Уструшаны в эпоху античности и раннего средневековья // ВЕСТНИК МИЦАИ. Вып. 23. Самарканд, 2016. – С. 92.

¹⁶ Холматов А., Холматов З. Тулкиликамар янги коятош расмлари хусусида айрим мулоҳазалар... 3-10

asked why there are so many pictures of mountain goats and other wild animals on the rocks here, they said, "Our ancestors After hunting a wild animal, a hunter left a picture of it on a rock. The reason is that this wild animal that was hunted has not completely left the mountain, its spirit remains here." This ethnographic information also confirms the opinion of the experts mentioned above. For example, the ancient hunters did not want these wild animals, which are a gift of nature, to be completely destroyed or to leave these lands, and on the contrary, they created the ground for their careful reproduction.

In conclusion, it can be said that our country is one of the promising countries in the study of rock paintings. This can be observed from the results of research conducted in recent years. However, due to the fact that such monuments are located in wide open natural areas, there are some problems in their preservation. It can be said that the level of preservation of his paintings today is very bad. Because one of the main problems in preserving this type of archeological monuments today is the removal of rock paintings. As a result, the future fate of such historical and cultural monuments left by our ancestors is in danger. Its preservation should be one of our main tasks.